

Introduction-Consent

Creative Commons License Use Survey for Language-Related Digital Creations

This survey is designed to understand how creators use (or decide not to use) Creative Commons licenses. The target survey participants are people who create materials for documentation, maintenance, instruction, learning, and/or revitalization of Indigenous, minority, and/or low-resourced languages.

Part 1 of this survey is designed to learn about the digital creation formats and sharing practices in this specific community of practice. Parts 2 through 4 of this survey contain general questions intended to elicit information about research participants'

- knowledge and awareness of Creative Commons (CC) licenses;
- understanding of how to apply CC licenses to their digital creations;
- interest in and experience with applying CC licenses to their digital creations;
- motivations for and barriers to applying CC licenses to their digital creations;
- understanding of how to adapt or reuse digital creations licensed with CC licenses.

This survey begins with a consent form.

Informed Consent: Creative Commons License Use on Language-Related Digital Creations

Please follow the link to the [Informed Consent Document](#) (clicking the link will open the document in a new tab). This document contains information to help you decide whether or not you wish to participate in this survey. Your participation in this project is completely voluntary. After reading the Informed Consent Document, please return to this window to proceed with the Informed Consent process.

Do you consent to participate in this survey?

Yes

No (Selecting this option will immediately end the survey)

Part 1: Your Language-related Digital Creations

Part 1: Your Digital Creations

This section contains questions about the kinds of digital materials that you create for the purpose of activities associated with **documentation, maintenance, instruction, learning, and/or revitalization of Indigenous, minority, and/or low-resourced languages** and how you share these materials or make them available to others.

“Digital materials” refers to any digital media files in any format that you consider to be the result of or useful for language documentation, maintenance, instruction, learning, and/or revitalization efforts. From this point on, these materials will be referred to as your **language-related digital creations**, or simply your **creations**.

For the purposes of this survey, it does not matter if you are the sole creator of these creations, or if you were a co-creator, i.e., a member of a team of people who collaborated to create the creations. Please consider all of these to be your creations.

What digital formats do you create? (Select all that apply)

audio/video

audio only (no video)

video only (no audio)

photographs

maps

digital art (e.g., drawings, animations, cartoons, other graphics, infographics, etc.)

text-based files (e.g., dictionaries, articles, essays, blog posts, books, databases, etc.)

open educational resources (OER)

apps (interactive applications or programs)

other (please specify)

Which of these digital platforms have you used to share your creations with other people (team members, classmates, collaborators, the general public on that platform, anyone at all)? (Select all that apply)

A digital repository or language archive (e.g., AILLA, ELAR, GitHub, TROLLing, Zenodo, FigShare, Mukurtu, university-based data or institutional repository, a tribal or community-based digital repository)

Video-sharing platforms (YouTube, Vimeo, etc.)

Audio-sharing platforms (SoundCloud, Spotify, Apple Podcasts, Google Podcasts, etc.)

Social media platforms (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, Reddit, TikTok, etc.)

Photo-sharing platforms (Flickr, Google Photos, etc.)

Wikimedia Foundation platforms (Wikimedia Commons, Wikibooks, Wiktionary, Wikiversity, Wikidata)

Cloud-based storage (GoogleDrive, DropBox, OneDrive, etc.)

Instant messaging platforms (WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Skype, Slack, etc.)

Website or blog (personal, community, school)

Writing/blogging platform (Medium, Patreon, Ghost, Write.as, etc.)

Traditional publishing, non-open access (books, journals, magazines)

Open access publishing (books, journals, magazines)

Open Educational Resources (OER), via OER publishers, websites, learning management systems

Email

I have never shared a language-related digital creation

Other (please specify)

Part 2: Applying Creative Commons Licenses

Part 2: Applying Creative Commons Licenses to Your Language-related Digital Creations

This section asks questions about your use of Creative Commons licenses on your own language-related digital creations. Please read the following definitions before answering the questions in this section. These definitions are available [here](#) (link opens in a new tab) for easier access as you answer the questions in this section.

- *Copyright*: a set of several rights that automatically apply to a creative work at the moment it is created. These rights belong exclusively to the creator of the work for

the duration of their life, and to their heir(s) for a set number of years (50 to 100, depending on the jurisdiction) after the creator's death. Thereafter, the work passes into the public domain.

- *Public Domain*: a body of expressed knowledge, ideas, and creativity to which copyright does not apply. Anyone in the world may use works in the public domain free of charge and for any purpose; thus, under the Western belief system, the public domain benefits everyone.
- *Open licenses*: open licenses, like the Creative Commons licenses, work in conjunction with copyright and can be applied to a creation that is protected by copyright. They help ensure that creations will not be locked into copyright's "all rights reserved" model for 50 to 100 years past the lifetime of the creators, and that other people will be able share, copy, and adapt these works, according to the terms of the open license.
- *Licensor*: the person who owns the copyrights to a creation and allows, by means of a license, someone else to use some of those copyrights.
- *Licensee*: the person to whom the license is granted; also, the person who is given permission, by means of a license, to copy, share, or adapt a copyrighted creation.
- *Adaptation, remix, derivative work*: a creation that is based on another work or on multiple other works. In the Creative Commons ecosystem, the terms *adaptation*, *remix*, and *derivative work* are used interchangeably.

Have you previously heard of Creative Commons licenses?

Yes

Not sure

No

Have you previously heard of the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication Tool? This also called CC0 or CC-Zero. When you apply CC-Zero to your creation, you give up all of your copyrights and dedicate your creation to the public domain.

Yes

Not sure

No

Have you ever seen any of these logos, licenses, or tools? (Select all that apply)

Creative Commons logo

Creative Commons Attribution license (CC BY)

Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike license (CC BY-SA)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial license (CC BY-NC)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike license (CC BY-NC-SA)

Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivatives license (CC BY-ND)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives license (CC BY-NC-ND)

Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication tool (CC0)

I have never seen any of these

Have you ever received or taken any of the following kinds of training about how to use Creative Commons licenses? (Select all that apply)

I have never received or taken any training on how to use Creative Commons licenses.

I completed the Creative Commons Certificate Course (<https://certificates.creativecommons.org/>).

I attended a training/workshop (live or online) offered by a library, archive, museum, school, or other organization.

I read about CC licenses on the Creative Commons website.

I read about CC licenses on Wikipedia.

Other (Please specify)

How confident do you feel in your understanding of what the CC licenses mean when you see them on digital media?

Very Confident

Somewhat confident

Neutral

Somewhat unconfident

Not at all confident

Have you ever been required to apply a CC license to your own creation? (e.g., publishing in an open access journal; contributing to the Wikimedia ecosystem; following a policy of your university or funder; following instructions for a class or course assignment; etc.)

Yes

Maybe

No

What person or organization required you to put a CC license on your creation? (Select all that apply)

A teacher, professor, or workshop facilitator

An Elder

A boss or supervisor

Open access journal or publisher

Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons, other Wikimedia platform

My school or university

My grant/fellowship/scholarship funder

I can't remember

Other

To what media formats were you required to apply a CC license? (Select all that apply)

audio/video

audio only (no video)

video only (no audio)

photographs

maps

digital art (e.g., drawings, animations, cartoons, other graphics, infographics, etc.)

text-based files (e.g., dictionaries, articles, essays, blog posts, books, databases, etc.)

open educational resources (OER)

apps (interactive applications or programs)

I can't remember

other (please specify)

When you were required to apply a CC license to your own creation, which license did you use? (Select all that apply)

Creative Commons Attribution license (CC BY)

Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike license (CC BY-SA)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial license (CC BY-NC)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike license (CC BY-NC-SA)

Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivatives license (CC BY-ND)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives license (CC BY-NC-ND)

Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication tool (CC0)

I can't remember

Have you ever voluntarily chosen to apply a CC license to your own creation (i.e., you were not required to do so)?

Yes

Maybe

No

To what media formats did you choose to apply a CC license? (Select all that apply)

audio/video

audio only (no video)

video only (no audio)

photographs

maps

digital art (e.g., drawings, animations, cartoons, other graphics, infographics, etc.)

text-based files (e.g., dictionaries, articles, essays, blog posts, books, databases, etc.)

open educational resources (OER)

apps (interactive applications or programs)

I can't remember

other (please specify)

Which license did you choose to apply to your creation? (Select all that apply)

Creative Commons Attribution license (CC BY)

Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike license (CC BY-SA)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial license (CC BY-NC)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike license (CC BY-NC-SA)

Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivatives license (CC BY-ND)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives license (CC BY-NC-ND)

Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication tool (CC0)

I can't remember

Have you ever used, or would you ever use, a CC license with the ND (No Derivatives) element? (CC BY-ND or CC BY-NC-ND)

Definitely yes

Probably yes

Neutral

Probably not

Definitely not

Why or why not? (ND, No Derivatives)

Have you ever used, or would you ever use, a CC license with the NC (Non-Commercial) element? (CC BY-NC or CC BY-NC-ND or CC BY-NC-SA)

Definitely yes

Probably yes

Neutral

Probably not

Definitely not

Why or why not? (NC, Non-Commercial)

Have you ever used, or would you ever use, a CC license with the SA (ShareAlike) element?
(CC BY-SA or CC BY-NC-SA)

Definitely yes

Probably yes

Neutral

Probably not

Definitely not

Why or why not? (SA, ShareAlike)

To what percentage of your creations do you apply CC licenses?

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

% of creations with
CC licenses

How confident do you feel in your understanding of how to apply CC licenses to your creations?

Very confident

Somewhat confident

Neutral

Somewhat unconfident

Not at all confident

Have you ever applied some other open license to your creations? (Select all that apply)

No

I can't remember

GNU General Public License

Open Data Commons license

Other

Part 3: Motivations & Barriers

Part 3: Motivations for and Barriers to Using Creative Commons Licenses

This section contains questions designed to understand your motivations for and barriers to using Creative Commons licenses to openly license your language-related digital creations.

Have you ever been motivated to apply a Creative Commons license to your own creations in order to do any of the following activities? (Select all that apply)

To participate in the Wikimedia ecosystem (Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons, Wikidata, etc.).

To participate in a competition or contest (e.g., photography, essay, short story, video, etc.).

To submit an application for a grant, fellowship, scholarship.

To promote open access.

To promote open knowledge.

To participate in the open movement.

To promote equity of access to digital media content.

Other (please specify)

Have you ever considered applying a CC license to your own creation, but then decided not to?

Yes

Maybe

No

What prevented you from applying a CCL to your creation? (Select all that apply)

I did not know which CC license to use.

I could not decide which CC license to use.

I could not find information that explained the CC licenses.

I did not understand copyright well enough to apply/pick a CC license.

I did not understand that CC licenses work in conjunction with copyright.

I did not think that a creation needs to be licensed since I can just share it however I want.

If I can't make money from my creation, I don't want anyone else to either.

I decided that I did not want to share my creation.

I did not want other people to be able to share my creation.

I did not want other people to be able to adapt or remix my creation.

I did not want someone from outside my culture to share/adapt/remix my creation about my culture/language

I decided that it was not appropriate to claim copyright ownership over traditional cultural expressions or knowledge.

The copyright is not mine to claim, so I cannot license the creation.

I was not sure if the content of my creation qualifies for copyright protection or not.

The content of my creation (e.g., ethnobotanical terms) probably did not qualify for copyright protection; therefore, I cannot license it.

Other

Do you think that Creative Commons licenses are appropriate ways to license your language-related digital creations?

Definitely yes

Probably yes

Neutral

Probably not

Definitely not

Why or why not?

Think about the **content** (not the format) of your language-related creations. Here are some examples, but please think about your own materials:

- videos to teach language use
- videos of oral histories from an Origin community
- videos demonstrating cultural practices
- picture and word books to teach vocabulary
- blog posts about community-related topics
- academic journal articles
- ethnobotanical databases
- dictionary databases

Of the digital media that you create, would it be appropriate to apply Creative Commons licenses to any of these materials based on their content (not their format)?

CC licenses are appropriate for the content of **ALL** of my creations.

CC licenses are appropriate for the content of **SOME** of my creations.

CC licenses are appropriate for the content of **NONE** of my creations.

Please explain.

Part 4: Reusing CC-licensed Creations

Part 4: Reusing CC-licensed Creations

This section will ask you questions about how you use and interact with CC-licensed creations that were created by other people. Please read the following definition before answering the questions in this section. This definition is available [here](#) (link opens in a new tab) for easier access as you answer the questions in this section.

- *Adaptation, remix, derivative work*: a creation that is based on another work or on multiple other works. In the Creative commons ecosystem, the terms *adaptation*, *remix*, and *derivative work* are used interchangeably.

Have you ever shared CC-licensed creations that were created by other people?
For example, have you shared them via any of the digital sharing platforms listed in Part 1?
(To see this list again, click [here](#); the link will open in a new tab.)

Yes

Maybe

No

Have you ever adapted/remixed/reused CC-licensed creations to make a new creation?

Yes

Maybe

No

Did you apply a CC license to your resulting adaptation/remix/derivative creation(s)?

Yes

Maybe

No

Which license did you choose to apply to your adaptation/remix/derivative creation(s)?
(Select all that apply)

Creative Commons Attribution license (CC BY)

Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike license (CC BY-SA)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial license (CC BY-NC)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike license (CC BY-NC-SA)

Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivatives license (CC BY-ND)

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives license (CC BY-NC-ND)

Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication tool (CC0)

I can't remember

How confident do you feel in your understanding of how to *share* CC-licensed creations that were created by other people?

Very Confident

Somewhat confident

Neutral

Somewhat unconfident

Not at all confident

How confident do you feel in your understanding of how to *adapt/remix/reuse* CC-licensed creations that were created by other people?

Very Confident

Somewhat confident
Neutral
Somewhat unconfident
Not at all confident

How confident do you feel in your understanding of how to *apply a CC license to an adaptation/remix/derivative work* that you created using other CC-licensed creations?

Very Confident
Somewhat confident
Neutral
Somewhat unconfident
Not at all confident

For which of the following purposes would you be interested in adapting/reusing/remixing CC-licensed creations? (Select all that apply)

To get new ideas and inspiration or to spark creativity.

To supplement my existing language-related creations to help facilitate my work.

To make them relevant to or useable by Origin community members, collaborators, team members, language learners, or other people (e.g., translating a creation into a different language, etc.).

To recreate the concept of the creation, but in a context that is relevant to my work/community.

I have no interest in using/reusing/remixing/adapting CC-licensed creations.

Other (please specify)

Which of the following do you see as barriers (for you or your collaborators) to using/reusing/remixing/adapting/sharing CC-licensed creations? (Select all that apply)

Not knowing where/how to find CC-licensed creations.

Not having time to search for CC-licensed creations that are relevant to my specific context (work, culture, language, Origin Community, etc.).

Difficulty finding CC-licensed creations that are relevant to my specific context (work, culture, language, Origin Community, etc.).

Difficulty changing or editing CC-licensed creations.

Not knowing if I have permission to modify the CC-licensed creations.

Not knowing if I am allowed to sell my adaptation/remix/derivative of a CC-licensed creation.

Difficulty integrating the CC-licensed creations into the technology I use.

Not enough time to experiment with adapting/remixing/reusing CC-licensed creations.

Lack of connections with other people who adapt/remix/reuse CC-licensed creations.

Difficulty getting collaborators to accept the practice of adapting/remixing/reusing CC-licensed creations.

Other (please specify)

Conclusion

Thank You!

Your time is a valuable gift. Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey. If you have follow-up questions, please contact the Principal Investigator, [Insert name and email].

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The Consent Form in this survey is a reuse, with slight adaptations, of the consent form presented in [Identifying OER Needs by Discipline](#) © 2018 by Abbey Elder, [CC BY 4.0](#). Some of the questions in this current survey are likewise inspired by or adapted from Elder 2018.

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If you would like to learn more about Creative Commons licenses, the [Creative Commons Certificate Course](#) is an excellent resource to learn more about the licenses, as well as their use and the open knowledge community which supports them.